

Faculty Perceptions, Experiences and Institutional Strategies for AI Integration

Dear Respondent,

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this survey.

Ashesi University, a member of a global consortium comprising the World Innovation Summit for Education (WISE), the Institute for International Education (IIE) and seven universities around the world, is conducting a research study on the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on higher education and the workforce in Africa. The study aims to understand how AI is currently influencing teaching and learning, institutional support and strategies for the integration of AI in higher education, as well as the evolving needs of employers as AI becomes more integrated into the world of work.

As a faculty member, you are invited to answer the following questions to provide insights into faculty perceptions and experiences with AI technologies, institutional interventions and policies, and prospects for future use. The estimated time for completing the survey is 9 to 12 minutes.

Participation in this research study is voluntary. By filling and submitting this form, you are consenting to the collection and use of the data provided for research purposes. Be assured that your responses are completely anonymous and will be aggregated with other data for reporting purposes. You may choose to stop participating at any time, without any penalty, before you click the "submit" button of the survey.

There are no foreseen risks in participating in this survey. This study and its data collection instruments have been reviewed and approved by the Ashesi IRB for Human Subjects Research (Application Number 52024). For further information, please contact the committee at irb@ashesi.edu.gh. You may also contact the Principal Investigators for this study through akorsah@ashesi.edu.gh.

Thank you for your time and contribution to this important research. Your input will help shape future strategies for AI integration in higher education.

* Required

Section A: Demographic Information

1. What is your age? *

- Under 30
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60 or above

2. Sex? *

- Male
- Female

3. Type of academic institution *

- Public University
- Private University
- Public Technical University

4. What is your rank? *

- Assistant Lecturer
- Lecturer/Senior Lecturer
- Associate Professor/Professor
- Other

5. What is your primary academic discipline? *

- Computer Science/Computer Engineering
- Other Information Technology related disciplines
- Other Engineering disciplines
- Business/Social Sciences
- Arts/Humanities
- Natural/Applied Sciences (including Mathematics, Statistics)
- Medical/Health-related disciplines
- Other

Section B: Familiarity and Perception of AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to technology that allows machines to perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence, such as learning, decision-making, and problem-solving. AI tools include generative tools (e.g. ChatGPT, Gemini, Midjourney), voice assistants (e.g., Siri, Alexa), recommendation systems (e.g., Netflix, YouTube), navigation apps (e.g., Google Maps), editorial & similarity detection tools (e.g., Grammarly, Turnitin) etc.

This section seeks to understand your familiarity and perception of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

6. How familiar are you with generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies/ tools such as ChatGPT, Gemini etc? *

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar

7. How familiar are you with non-generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies/ tools, e.g. recommendation and navigation systems? *

- Not at all familiar
- Slightly familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Moderately familiar
- Very familiar

8. To what extent do you agree that AI technologies have the potential to enhance teaching, research, and administrative processes in Higher Educational Institutions? *

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

9. How do you perceive the role of AI in changing traditional approach to academic activities in Higher Educational Institutions? (Select all that apply) *

- Enhancing teaching effectiveness
- Personalising learning experiences
- Facilitating student engagement
- Disrupting traditional teaching methods
- Job displacement
- Accelerating research progress
- Enabling new research methodologies
- Reducing reliance on human researchers
- Introducing ethical concerns
- Administrative tasks related to teaching (e.g. Creating assessments, grading)
- Other

10. How do you feel about incorporating AI technologies into the various activities as a faculty member? *

	Very Resistant	Apprehensive	Neutral / Indifferent	Excited	Very Excited
Teaching and Assessment	<input type="radio"/>				
Research Activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Administrative Activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Personal Activities	<input type="radio"/>				

11. In your opinion, how important is it for faculty members to embrace AI technologies in higher education? *

- Not Important
- Somewhat Important
- Neutral
- Important
- Very Important

12. To what extent do you currently consider the existence of AI technologies when developing or modifying your course content and assessments? *

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I actively incorporate AI insights and trends in my course content development.	<input type="radio"/>				
I adjust my assessments to prioritise original student work over tasks that AI can assist with.	<input type="radio"/>				
I seek information on how AI can enhance student learning experiences and modify my teaching methods accordingly.	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Have you used/plan to use any AI technologies in any aspect of your work as a faculty member (such as teaching, administrative and research tasks)? *

- Yes
- No

14. What is/are the **main** reason(s) you have not used AI tools *

- Lack of knowledge or training in AI tools
- Ethical concerns about the use AI in academic settings (e.g. related to academic integrity)
- Limited access to AI tools and infrastructure
- AI tools are not sufficiently integrated into the curriculum
- Other

15. How likely are you to incorporate AI technologies into your teaching, research, or administrative tasks in the future? *

- Very unlikely
- Unlikely
- Neutral
- Likely
- Very likely

Section C : Usage of AI

16. How frequently do you currently use AI tools in your work as a faculty member? *

- Never** - I do not use AI tools at all.
- Rarely** - I use AI tools infrequently.
- Sometimes** - I use AI tools from time to time in my work
- Often** - I regularly use AI tools for some of my work activities.
- Almost Always** - I use AI tools in most of my work activities.

17. In what area(s) do you use/intend to use AI in your work as a faculty member? Select all that apply *

- Research
- Teaching & Assessment
- Administrative
- Other

18. What kind of tasks / activities have you used/plan to AI technologies for? (Select all that apply) *

- Research assistance (e.g., finding sources, summarizing articles)
- Writing support (e.g., drafting essays, grammar checks)
- Data analysis (e.g., processing or analyzing datasets)
- Problem-solving (e.g., coding help, solving equations)
- Study aid (e.g., flashcards, personalized learning recommendations)
- Presentation creation (e.g., generating slides, designing visuals)
- Project planning or organization (e.g., task management, brainstorming)
- Tutoring or learning new topics (e.g., explanations, answering questions)
- Preparing course materials (e.g., content, examples, case studies)
- Other

19. Which AI technologies or tools have you used? (Select all that apply) *

- Chatbots (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini)
- AI-based research tools (e.g., SciSpace, Elicit, Phind)
- Data analysis tools (e.g., Tableau, Power BI)
- AI writing assistants (e.g., Grammarly, Quilbot)
- Image / Video Generation (DALL-E)
- Presentation Preparation (Gamma, Canva etc)
- Other

20. Have you incorporated AI into your teaching in any of the following ways? (Select All that apply) *

- Given an assignment or assessment that requires students to use an AI tool
- Demonstrated the use of an AI tool in a class that you teach
- Encouraged students to use AI for self-study in a class that you teach
- Preparing course materials (e.g., content, examples, case studies)
- Other

21. How would you describe your level of expertise with AI technologies and tools? *

- Basic Understanding** - I have a fundamental knowledge of AI concepts but have not used AI tools extensively.
- User** - I have utilised AI tools for simple tasks or applications in my work or studies
- Adaptor** - can adapt AI tools to solve specific problems and have experience using APIs and other resources
- Developer** - actively develop or create AI technologies, such as training models and implementing AI solutions
- Innovator** - I am a producer of AI technologies, leading projects or creating new AI applications and systems.

22. How did you attain this level of AI competence you rated yourself above? (Select all that apply) *

- Attending workshops, conferences, or webinars
- Engaging in online courses or self-study
- Collaborating with colleagues or researchers in the field.
- Reading academic journals and publications.
- As part of my undergraduate/graduate program.
- News/Social Media
- Other

23. What motivates you to use AI technologies in your work as a faculty member? (Select all that apply) *

- Saves time on routine tasks (e.g., speed in evaluating large class sizes)
- Keeping up with technological advancements
- Meeting institutional requirements (e.g., key performance indicators)
- Improved student engagement and learning outcomes
- Personalised learning experiences (e.g., tailored study materials)
- Enhanced efficiency and productivity
- Improved research efficiency (e.g., faster access to information)
- Other

24. What benefits or positive outcomes have you experienced from using AI technologies in your role as a faculty member? (Select all that apply) *

- Saves time on routine tasks (e.g., speed in evaluating large class sizes)
- Keeping up with technological advancements
- Fear of job insecurity due to the rising skill gap
- Meeting institutional requirements (e.g., key performance indicators)
- Improved student engagement and learning outcomes
- Personalised learning experiences (e.g., tailored study materials)
- Enhanced efficiency and productivity
- Improved research efficiency (e.g., faster access to information)
- Other

25. What are the main challenges or negative outcomes, if any, you have encountered while using AI technologies? (Select all that apply) *

- Technical issues or limitations (e.g., software glitches, connectivity issues lack of infrastructure)
- Difficulty integrating AI into academic work or curriculum
- Resistance from colleagues, students, or administration
- Ethical concerns (e.g., fairness, privacy, or academic integrity)
- Lack of training or understanding of AI tools
- Cost in accessing AI tools (e.g. Chat GPT 4, etc.)
- Other

26. What dangers, if any, does continuous use of AI pose to your work as a faculty member? (Select all that apply) *

- Privacy and data security concerns
- Lack of transparency or interpretability in AI systems
- Loss of human touch or creativity
- Academic integrity/honesty
- Job displacement of educators
- Other

27. How has your perception of AI changed as your expertise in using it has developed? *

- Significant negative change
- Slight negative change
- No change
- Slight positive change
- Significant positive change

28. Please elaborate on your response to the previous question about how your perception of AI has changed.

29. Overall, how has the use of AI tools impacted your work as a faculty member? *

- Highly Negatively
- Negatively
- Neutral
- Positively
- Highly Positively

Section D: Concerns about Privacy and Ethical Implications

30. How concerned are you about the potential privacy and ethical implications associated with the adoption of AI technologies in Higher Educational Institutions? *

- Very unconcerned
- Unconcerned
- Neutral
- Concerned
- Very Concerned

31. What specific privacy risks concerns do you associate with the use of AI technologies in Higher Educational Institutions? (Select all that apply) *

- Misuse/Unauthorised access to sensitive data
- Potential lack of anonymity
- Lack of transparency in data collection and usage practices.
- Data breaches and security vulnerabilities
- Other

32. How concerned are you about the potential for bias in AI algorithms used in Higher Educational Institutions? *

- Very unconcerned
- Unconcerned
- Neutral
- Concerned
- Very Concerned

33. What potential biases do you identify in existing AI tools used in your work as faculty? (Select all that apply) *

- Gender bias** - Unequal treatment based on gender in AI decisions.
- Racial bias** - Unfair outcomes stemming from race or ethnicity in AI systems.
- Socioeconomic bias** - Disadvantages individuals due to their economic status in AI applications.
- Disability bias** - Neglecting the needs of individuals with disabilities in AI design.
- Algorithmic Bias** - Discrimination caused by biased data or algorithms in AI processes
- Regional bias** - Favouring specific geographic regions, impacting fairness and effectiveness.
- Other

34. Please elaborate on your response to the previous question about potential biases you may have identified in existing AI tools. Name the tools and the bias you identified, if possible.

35. In your opinion, what measures should be implemented in Higher Education Institutions to address privacy and ethical issues in the use of AI technologies?

Section E: Institutional Interventions

We are now transitioning to a section that explores institutional interventions, policies, and strategies related to AI usage. Your insights on these topics will help us understand how institutions are adapting to the integration of AI technologies

36. To what extent has your institution supported the adoption and integration of AI technologies in teaching and student learning? *

- Not at all
- Not much
- Neutral
- Somewhat
- Very much

37. Rate your institution's policies and strategies to support AI adoption based on the following statements, using a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My institution has clear policies regarding the use of AI in teaching, research and administrative tasks	<input type="radio"/>				
My institution has clear policies regarding students' use of AI in their submitted work.	<input type="radio"/>				
My institution's strategic plan includes the integration of AI in teaching and learning	<input type="radio"/>				
My institution has allocated sufficient budget and resources for AI-driven education initiatives	<input type="radio"/>				
My institution has a dedicated unit or team for overseeing, enforcing and supporting the policies and strategies related to the use or adoption of AI.	<input type="radio"/>				

38. Rate your institution's infrastructure and technology support for AI adoption based on the following statements, using a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My institution has acquired / subscribed to tools and infrastructure to support integration of AI into teaching and learning.	<input type="radio"/>				
The technology infrastructure at my institution (e.g., internet, devices, software) supports effective use of AI.	<input type="radio"/>				
AI tools are easily accessible to both faculty and students at my institution.	<input type="radio"/>				

39. Rate your institution's training of faculty to support AI adoption based on the following statements, using a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My institution provides sufficient training for faculty on how to integrate AI into their teaching methods.	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel adequately supported by my institution when learning about AI technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Continuous professional development related to AI integration is available at my institution.	<input type="radio"/>				

40. Rate your institution's support to students in using AI in academic work based on the following statements, using a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My institution provides adequate support for students to use AI tools in their learning.	<input type="radio"/>				
Students are actively encouraged to explore and use AI in their academic work.	<input type="radio"/>				
AI tools enhance student engagement and learning outcomes in my institution.	<input type="radio"/>				

41. Rate your institution's ethical considerations on the responsible use of AI. *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
My institution has clear ethical guidelines on the responsible use of AI in education.	<input type="radio"/>				
The institution promotes awareness of AI's potential biases and its implications in education.	<input type="radio"/>				
There are mechanisms in place to ensure the ethical and equitable use of AI technologies at my institution.	<input type="radio"/>				

42. Additional comments on any aspect of this survey

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